

SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pARticle Data (SPEARHEAD)

Funded by
the European Union

Deliverable 2.1

Geant4 models, part I

EU's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme

Grant Agreement 101135044

UNIVERSITY
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Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel

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Work Package	WP2: Instrument response
Task	Task 2-1
Deliverable	D2.1: GEANT4 models, Part I.
Date for Deliverable	27 December 2024

Change Log				
Version	Date	Author(s)	Reason for Modification	Status
1	2024-12-27	Köberle et al.	New Document	Submitted
2				

Dissemination Level	
Public	X
Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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List of Acronyms

AMS	Alpha Magnet Spectrometer
BepiC	BepiColombo
CAD	Computer-Aided Design
COSTEP	Comprehensive Suprathermal and Energetic Particle Analyzer
D	Deliverable
EPD	Energetic Particle Detector
EPHIN	Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument
ERNE	Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron experiment
ESA	European Space Agency
G4VM	Geant4 Virtual Machine
GCR	Galactic Cosmic Ray
GDML	Geometry Description Markup Language
GEANT	GEometry ANd Tracking
HED	High Energy Detector
HET	High Energy Telescope
JAXA	Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency
LED	Low Energy Detector
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
PAMELA	Payload for Antimatter Matter Exploration and Light-nuclei Astrophysics
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SIXS	Solar Intensity X-ray and particle Spectrometer
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SoIO	Solar Orbiter
SPEARHEAD	SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
SQ	Science Question
STEP	Standard for the Exchange of Product model data
TO	Technical Objective
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document reports on the implementation of the [GEANT4](#) models for [SOHO/Chandra - EPHIN](#), [SOHO-Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron experiment \(ERNE\)](#), [SolO-High Energy Telescope \(HET\)](#) and [BepiColombo \(BepiC\)-Solar Intensity X-ray and particle Spectrometer \(SIXS\)](#).

The general procedure for determining the response functions for particle instruments is outlined in the introduction.

Section 2 provides an overview on the Geometry Description Markup Language ([GDML](#)) schema used to implement the geometry and material composition of the instruments in [GEANT4](#).

In Sect. 3, the individual models for each instrument are briefly described, highlighting the realistic implementation in comparison with the actual instruments. The models for [SOHO/Chandra - EPHIN](#) and [SolO-HET](#) are distributed within the scope of the [G4VM](#) (see Deliverable (D)6.2) allowing a readily accessible simulation. A manual for setting up the [G4VM](#) is given in Appendices A.1, A.2, and A.3.

1 Introduction

SPeCification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data (**SPEARHEAD**) will provide answers to three Science Questions (**SQs**):

1. How are protons accelerated beyond 100 MeV and electrons beyond 1 MeV in solar eruptions?
2. What are the release times and spectral characteristics of near-relativistic particles from solar eruptions?
3. How do coronal and interplanetary structures affect the transport processes of very high energetic particles?

To enable the scientific data analysis **SPEARHEAD** has three Technical Objective (**TO**):

1. Determining the response functions of a large number of spacecraft instruments to derive high-energy particle fluxes from observations at unprecedented accuracy releasing revised and completely new datasets
2. Performing cross-calibration of datasets measured by science-grade and monitoring instruments to enable the use of monitoring data for scientific analyses
3. Combining high-energy particle and context observations together with modeling of plasma structures for easier in-depth analysis of solar eruptions, quantifying their effect and delivering them to the community.

Hereby Work Package (**WP**)2 directly addresses **TO1** and supports **TO2**.

Efficiency computation for space particle instruments like **EPHIN** (Müller-Mellin et al. 1995) aboard **SOHO** of European Space Agency (**ESA**) and National Aeronautics and Space Administration (**NASA**), **EPHIN** aboard **Chandra** of **NASA**, **ERNE** (Torsti et al. 1995) aboard **SOHO**, **HET** (Rodríguez-Pacheco et al. 2020) aboard **SoLo** of **ESA**, and **SIXS** (Huovelin et al. 2020) aboard **BepiC** of **ESA** and Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (**JAXA**) involves quantifying the instrument's ability to detect and measure particles accurately in a space environment. In more detail:

- Particle measurements consists of a set of measured quantities (like energy losses, photon detection etc.) typically quantified as count rates C .
- At a given time t the instrument is embedded in a radiation environment consisting of different ions, electrons, and photons that are the unknown physical quantities $J_\alpha(E, \Omega, \mathbf{x}, t)$ to be derived. Herein E , Ω , \mathbf{x} , and α are the kinetic Energy, the incoming direction, the location, and particle species, respectively.
- Both are interlinked by the Sullivan (Sullivan 1971) equation:

$$C(\mathbf{x}, t_0) = \frac{1}{T} \int_{t_0}^{t_0+T} dt \int_S \hat{\mathbf{r}} \cdot d\boldsymbol{\sigma} \int_\Omega d\omega \int_0^\infty dE \sum_\alpha \varepsilon_\alpha(E, \boldsymbol{\sigma}, \omega, t) J_\alpha(E, \omega, \mathbf{x}, t) \quad (1)$$

with:

J_α = spectral intensity of particle α

ε_α = detection efficiency of particle type α

t = time

t_0 = time at start of observation

T = total observation time

$d\sigma$ = element of surface area of the last telescope sensor to be penetrated

S = total area of the last telescope sensor

$d\omega$ = element of solid angle

Ω = domain of ω ; this is limited by the other telescope sensors

\mathbf{x} = spatial coordinate of the telescope

$\hat{\mathbf{r}}$ = unit vector in direction ω

$\hat{\mathbf{r}} \cdot d\sigma$ = effective element of area looking into ω

Efficiency typically depends on factors such as the geometry, material properties, detection mechanisms, and energy thresholds of the instrument. The following is a workflow for computing the efficiency for a spacecraft instrument (a general simplified setup is described by [Sullivan 1971](#), and citing authors):

Define Instrument Geometry and Setup: As discussed in detail by [Sullivan \(1971\)](#) for simple instrument geometry the geometric factor can be computed analytically. The geometric factor G of a single detector of arbitrary shape with a surface A for instance is given by $G = \pi \cdot A$. Utilizing a more complex instrument, the geometrical efficiency can be computed by a Monte-Carlo method choosing randomly a starting point on one of the instrument planes and an isotropic direction. Then one computes the intersection of the track with all the material involved, i.e., other detectors that define a valid measurement for the instrument. Then the **geometrical efficiency** (ϵ_g) is given by:

$$\epsilon_g = \frac{\text{Number of particles that intersect the detector}}{\text{Total number of incident particles}}$$

This depends on the acceptance angle, size, and shape of the detector.

Determine Detector Response: In the above case the detector is taken as ideal with a detection sensitivity of 100% for the sensitive area and 0 outside. This might not be true, and a sensitivity model must be taken into account (an example is given by [Marquardt et al. 2015](#)), leading to the so-called **intrinsic efficiency** ϵ_i that is given by

$$\epsilon_i = \frac{\text{Number of particles detected}}{\text{Number of particles incident on the sensitive area}}$$

This is influenced by the detector material and energy sensitivity.

Energy and Particle Species Sensitivity: The interaction of particles – charged or neutral – depends on the physics of energy exchange due to, e.g., Coulomb energy losses, Bremsstrahlung, hadron interaction, photon interactions, but also to scattering and particle decay and can be complex, depending on the energy range and species of particles the instrument is designed to detect. The corresponding efficiency is often expressed as a function of energy and particle type:

$$\epsilon(E) = \epsilon_g \cdot \epsilon_i(E)$$

A simple example is an ideal telescope for which the energy response $R(E)$ is given by a function:

$$0 \text{ for } E < E_l \tag{2}$$

$$\epsilon_i(E) = 1 \text{ for } E_l \leq E \leq E_u \tag{3}$$

$$0 \text{ for } E > E_u \tag{4}$$

with an energy sensitivity of 1 only within the nominal energy interval between a lower and upper energy E_l and E_u , respectively.

In order to compute efficiencies with the above-mentioned method, Monte-Carlo simulations utilizing the [GEANT 4](#) toolkit ([Agostinelli et al. 2003](#)) are performed to model the particle interactions with the instrument and the total efficiency (details will be provided in the near future at [D2.3](#)). However, the computations need to be validated by comparing with calibration efforts using known particle sources or different instrumentation (for details see [D3.1](#); [Heber et al. \(2024\)](#)).

[D2.1](#); [Köberle et al. \(2024\)](#), sets the foundation for subsequent deliverables by providing and implementing accurate models of the instruments.

2 Structure of a GDML file

To describe and import complex geometries into [GEANT 4](#), the [GDML](#) interface was developed. [GDML](#) is an eXtensible Markup Language ([XML](#))-based language specifically designed for describing geometrical structures in [GEANT 4](#) simulations. The [GDML](#) schema utilized to define the simulation geometry is structured in six blocks, each containing specific types of information.

2.1 Overview of the primary blocks used in GDML files

Define The `<define>` block allows for the declaration of constants and transformations that can be reused throughout the geometry description:

- Constants: Numeric values, such as lengths or angles, can be defined and referenced by name.
- Transformations: Predefined translations, rotations, and scaling transformations simplify the placement of objects and can be applied consistently across multiple components.

Materials The `<materials>` block describes the materials used in the simulation:

- Includes definitions for elements, isotopes, and compounds.
- Specifies properties such as density, atomic composition, and state (solid, liquid, or gas).

Solids The `<solids>` block defines the geometric shapes used as the building blocks of the geometry:

- Primitive shapes include boxes, cylinders, and spheres.
- Complex shapes can be created using Boolean operations like union, intersection, and subtraction.

Structure The `<structure>` block organizes the geometry components and their hierarchical relationships:

Logical Volumes Logical volumes combine materials with solids:

- A logical volume is defined by assigning a material to a solid.
- Logical volumes are reusable components in the hierarchy.

Physical Volumes Physical volumes place logical volumes in the global coordinate system:

- Includes position, orientation, and scaling information.
- Supports parameterized placements for repeating patterns like arrays.

Nesting Logical and physical volumes are arranged hierarchically:

- Parent volumes can contain child volumes, enabling the modular construction of complex geometries.

Setup The `<setup>` block specifies the global configuration of the geometry:

- Declares the world volume, which is the outermost container for all geometry elements.
- Defines the starting point for simulation initialization.

Auxiliary User Information The `<userinfo>` block is optional, set after the structure block and provides user-defined metadata and annotations:

- Used to attach custom information, such as tags or properties, to **GDML** elements.
- Enables flexibility for advanced simulations and specialized applications.

2.2 Example GDML file

Below is an example **GDML** file taken from the **GDML** manual (see <https://gdml.web.cern.ch/GDML/doc/GDMLmanual.pdf> for additional information):

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<gdml xsi:noNamespaceSchemaLocation="schema/gdml.xsd">
  <define>
...
    <position name="TrackerinWorldpos" unit="mm" x="0" y="0" z="100"/>
  </define>
  <materials>
...
    <element name="Nitrogen" formula="N" Z="7.">
      <atom value="14.01"/>
    </element>
    <material formula=" " name="Air" >
      <D value="1.290" unit="mg/cm3"/>
      <fraction n="0.7" ref="Nitrogen" />
      <fraction n="0.3" ref="Oxygen" />
    </material>
  </materials>
  <solids>
...
    <box lunit="mm" name="Tracker" x="50" y="50" z="50"/>
  </solids>
  <structure>
...
    <volume name="World" >
      <materialref ref="Air" />
      <solidref ref="world" />
      <physvol>
        <volumeref ref="Tracker" />
        <positionref ref="TrackerinWorldpos"/>
        <rotationref ref="TrackerinWorldrot"/>
      </physvol>
    </volume>
  </structure>
  <setup name="Default" version="1.0" >
    <world ref="World" />
  </setup>
</gdml>
```


3 Description of instrument GDML files

In this section, the implementation of the instrument models in GDML is briefly described.

3.1 GDML of EPHIN aboard SOHO and Chandra

The GDML files for EPHIN aboard SOHO and Chandra are provided in the scope of the G4VM via the SPEARHEAD GitHub repository (D6.2; Gieseler et al. (2024)), available at <https://github.com/spearhead-he/G4VM>, with the aim of making the new GEANT4 models readily accessible. A detailed manual on how to set up the G4VM can be found in the Appendices A.1, A.2, and A.3. The G4VM repository contains one file of the raw instrument named `ephin.gdml`, and two files with the respective spacecraft model incorporated, named `ephin_soho_shield.gdml` and `ephin_chandra_shield.gdml`. The GDML files follow the general structure described in Sect. 2.2; however, for readability, groups of components are outsourced to separate folders and imported as entities at the beginning of the main GDML files. The following is a description of the groups and their content.

aluminum contains all housing components made of aluminum

anticoincidence contains the plastic scintillator serving as anticoincidence

deadlayer contains dead layer material of the detectors

delrin contains connections between anticoincidence and housing made out of Delrin

detector contains the silicon solid-state detectors

detector_passive contains the passive detector material

foils contains the Kapton and titanium foil shielding the telescope

shield contains the spacecraft models.

Figure 1 shows a sketch of EPHIN (left) and the visualization of the EPHIN GEANT model (right). The passive material of the housing, mainly consisting of aluminum, is shown in gray. The sensitive detectors are the six silicon solid state detectors A-F, color-coded in yellow, with A and B divided into six segments. The enclosed plastic scintillator that serves as an anti-coincidence is shown in blue.

Figure 2 shows in the upper left and right panels drawings of the SOHO and Chandra spacecraft indicating the position of ERNE and EPHIN (COSTEP), respectively. The implementations of the spacecraft models for EPHIN aboard SOHO (left) and Chandra (right) are shown in the lower panels. The spacecraft are modeled as spherical shells made of aluminum, where each shell segment has a different density attributed according to the spatial mass distribution of the spacecraft. The density of the individual shell segments is color coded, highlighting the different positions on the spacecraft and the substantially higher mass of Chandra (4800 kg) compared to SOHO (1850 kg). This approach of approximating the spacecraft matter results in a drastically reduced computation time and was also necessary for Chandra due to legal reasons that prohibit us from publishing representations of the original blueprints. The spacecraft model for Chandra is experimental and will be validated in the scope of D2.3, in the course of the SPEARHEAD project.

Figure 1: The left and right panels show a sketch and visualization of GDML geometry of the EPHIN sensor head aboard the SOHO and Chandra spacecraft, respectively. For clarity, one segment of A and B was not color-coded.

Figure 2: The upper left and right panels show drawings of the SOHO (adapted from Belov et al. 2021) and Chandra (<https://cxc.harvard.edu/proposer/POG/html/chap1.html>) spacecraft indicating the position of ERNE and EPHIN (COSTEP), respectively. The lower panels show on the left and right visualizations of GDML geometry of the EPHIN sensor head together with the simplified spacecraft model aboard the two spacecraft, respectively.

3.2 GDML of HET aboard SoIO

The Solar Orbiter (SoIO) High Energy Telescope (HET) is a state-of-the-art instrument designed to measure high-energy particles in the Sun's environment. It is part of the EPD suite aboard ESA's SoIO mission. HET detects and analyzes Solar Energetic Particles (SEPs), particularly protons, electrons and heavy ions, with energies ranging from a few MeV to more than hundreds of MeV for ions and between hundreds of keV to about 30 MeV for electrons (Rodríguez-Pacheco et al. 2020).

Using silicon detectors and advanced particle identification techniques like the $\frac{dE}{dx} - E$ and $\frac{dE}{dx} - \frac{dE}{dx}$ method, HET provides energy spectra in the energy ranges mentioned above (see for example Wimmer-Schweingruber et al. 2021; Kouloumvakos et al. 2024).

The GDML model of SoIO HET is also provided via the G4VM in two versions, one describing the raw instrument, named `HET.gdml`, and one with the spacecraft model included, named `HET_shield.gdml`. Parts of the GDML are outsourced, namely:

bgoandptfedefinition.gdml Definitions of the BGO-crystal and the crystal cage

bgoandptfevolume.gdml Volume definition of the BGO

hetadefinitions.gdml Definition of constants for the A detector

hetasolids.gdml Definition of the A detector volumes including carrier and guard ring

pcbvolumes.gdml Definition of the Printed Circuit Board (PCB) volumes

hetbdefinitions.gdml Definition of constants for the B detector

hetbsolids.gdml Definition of the B detector volumes including carrier and guard ring

shell Includes material as well as logical and physical volume definitions for the spacecraft model

An illustration of the instrument and its implementation is shown in Fig. 3 on the left and right, respectively. The segmented silicon detectors are color coded in red, and the central BGO scintillator crystal is color coded in blue. The right panel also displays the electronic box of the instrument in the background.

Figure 4 displays on the left and right a SoIO CAD view indicating the location of HET and the GDML implementation by a simplified spacecraft model, respectively. The spacecraft model is defined similarly to the ones of EPHIN as spherical shell segments of varying density, whereby the total launch mass of 1700 kg was considered to be composed of 200 kg of hydrazine fuel, 750 kg of aluminum, and 750 kg of PCB-like materials, following Freiherr von Forstner et al. (2021). PCB materials are generally made up of three elements that work together to meet the specific needs of the electronic system: Copper, Resin and Glass

Figure 3: The left and right panels show an illustration of the CAD model and visualization of GDML geometry of the HET sensor head aboard the SoIo spacecraft, respectively.

Figure 4: On the left and right are shown an EPD instrument suite CAD view of SoIo (Rodríguez-Pacheco et al. 2020) and a visualization of the GDML geometry of the HET sensor head without electronic box aboard SoIo together with the spacecraft model, respectively.

Figure 5: The left and right panels show a sketch and a visualization of the 300-element GDML geometry of the ERNE-HED sensor head aboard the SOHO spacecraft, respectively.

3.3 GDML of ERNE-HED aboard SOHO

The GEANT 4 model of SOHO / ERNE has been modernized based on a newly constructed CAD model of the instrument generated from the drawings. A simple spacecraft model (following Kühl et al. 2015) was also included to account for the additional shielding suffered by backward-penetrating particles. The instrument model has been converted to GDML. The GDML model includes the High Energy Detector (HED) (see the right panel of Fig. 5), the Low Energy Detector (LED) head (not shown here), the instrument electronics, and a shield below the sensor unit representing the spacecraft. The composition and density of the spacecraft material can be adjusted (at the moment, it is represented by an aluminum slab with a thickness of 1 cm and an approximate density of 27 g cm^{-3}).

The model was already used for full-sky GEANT 4 simulations for protons between 100 MeV and 10 GeV, allowing an expansion of the energy range to particles penetrating the whole stack, which have previously not been subjected to a scientific analysis. The model will still be upgraded with a new spacecraft model, similar to that described for SOHO / EPHIN above (see Fig. 2).

The GDML model consists of a single file and uses the default schema for GDML syntax. The volumes in the model are named according to the material and its density; for example, the Al10 prefix means that aluminum is ten times less dense than usual. Such naming allowed automated material assignment, which is less prone to single mistakes. Lower density in very thin films aims at reducing simulation errors. In case the density is lower, the metric dimensions are artificially and proportionally larger.

3.4 GDML of SIXS aboard BepiC

Some progress has also been made concerning the Solar Intensity X-ray and particle Spectrometer (SIXS) aboard BepiColombo (BepiC). In addition to response functions, effective energies for the particle channels were calculated. The graphical representation of the GDML model of the particle detection system of SIXS (SIXS-P) is shown in the left panel of Fig. 7. The model will be further improved to include the complete equivalent of the spacecraft to assess, e.g., electron scattering from the multilayer thermal shield obstructing the field of view of one of the viewing cones of SIXS-P in the cruise configuration.

Figure 6: The cross-section of the full GDML geometry of ERNE aboard the SOHO spacecraft.

Figure 7: The left and right panels show a sketch (from Huovelin et al. 2020, Fig. 8) and a visualization of the preliminary GDML geometry of the SIXS sensor head aboard the BepiC spacecraft, respectively.

4 Conclusions

The reliability of energetic particle measurements in space depends on several factors. These include the sensitivity and calibration of the detectors used, the shielding of the instruments against background radiation, and the stability of the spacecraft's environment. In more detail:

1. **Instrument Design, Sensitivity and Calibration:** The performance of particle detectors is heavily influenced by the design, their sensitivity to various particle species and energy ranges. Proper calibration of the instruments, both on the ground and in-flight, ensures accurate measurement of particle fluxes and energies. This has been detailed in (Heber et al. 2024)
2. **Background Noise and Contamination:** Energetic particle measurements can be affected by background noise from cosmic rays, secondary particles, or electronic interference. Effective shielding and noise filtering techniques are crucial to enhance measurement reliability.
3. **Redundancy and Cross-Validation (details can be found in Heber et al. 2024):** Using multiple instruments or missions to measure the same particle populations allows cross-validation of results. Redundancy in measurements increases confidence in the reliability of the observed data.
4. **Data Processing and Analysis Techniques:** The reliability of measurements also depends on the methods used to process and analyze raw data. Advanced algorithms for particle identification, energy calibration, and error correction play a significant role in reducing uncertainties (as addressed in Gieseler et al. 2024, and references therein).
5. **Mission Duration and Orbit:** The duration of the mission and the orbit of the spacecraft determine the range of space environments sampled. Long-term missions enable the study of both steady-state and transient phenomena, while specific orbits may provide access to critical regions such as the polar regions of the Sun or the inner heliosphere close to the Sun.
6. **Interpretation of Results:** Reliable interpretation of measurements requires accurate models of particle acceleration, transport, and interactions (see for example Vainio et al. 2024).

To enable scientific data analysis within SPEARHEAD, we went through the steps 1 to 4 and have determined the response function of SOHO Comprehensive Suprathermal and Energetic Particle Analyzer (COSTEP) EPHIN applying the methodology to the "raw" measurements of Galactic Cosmic Rays (GCRs) and validated the process using Alpha Magnet Spectrometer (AMS) and Payload for Antimatter Matter Exploration and Light-nuclei Astrophysics (PAMELA) measurements as described in detail in Heber et al. (2024). Essential for the process is a detailed model of the particle instrument involved and the spacecraft to which it is attached (Steps 1 and 2 above).

In this deliverable, we successfully implemented the sensor geometry and the spacecraft environment in a virtual machine that runs a pre-installed version of GEANT 4 for SOHO and Chandra EPHIN, SOHO ERNE, SoHO HET, and BepiC SIXS. These models will be used in D2.3 in order to compute the energy response functions that are needed as input to the bow-tie tool described in D6.2 (Gieseler et al. 2024) and provided via the SPEARHEAD GitHub¹.

¹<https://github.com/spearhead-he/bowtie>

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Appendix

1 G4VM manual

In this manual, we propose to build the [GEANT4](#) applications on a ready to use Virtual Machine (VM).

Our recommended setup requires three resources:

1. A Virtualization Software (VMware Workstation Player 17)
2. A Geant4 Virtual Machine
3. The [GEANT4](#) application source code

The usage of a VM on which the [GEANT4](#) applications are installed is by no means necessary or ideal but serves as a readily accessible way to get started, bypassing any dependency issues that frequently occur on individual sets of devices.

2 Virtual machine setup

Here, we describe the steps needed to set up a machine-independent VM.

Virtualization software is needed to be installed. For details, follow the description at the tutorial of the LP2i Bordeaux. The proposed setup has been tested using Workstation Player 17 obtained from VMware on MAC as well as Windows 11. However, an installation that uses Virtualbox is also supported.

Virtual Machine (VM): the compressed VM can then be downloaded from LP2i Bordeaux. You need to have at least ⚠️ $\approx 10\text{GB}$ compressed $\rightarrow \approx 20\text{GB}$ decompressed space on your hard disk. *The Release used throughout this manual is Geant4.11.2.1 as of 13/03/2024.*

Preparation: ⚠️ Before starting the VM you might want to "Edit virtual machine settings" such as the number of cores to allow for multithreading or exchange directories with the host system. For details, see the manual of your VM.

Installation: After decompressing, start the VMware Workstation Player and initialize the VM by clicking the "Open a Virtual Machine" button to select the VM configuration file. The VM should now be visible within the VMware Player library.

After powering on the machine for the first time, you will be asked whether you have copied or moved the VM, select "I copied it". You can now access a fully operational Linux system with [GEANT4](#) -4. There is a default user account; the log-in account is: `local1`, the password is also `local1`, the root password is `rocky9`.

⚠️ The default keyboard layout is French and might be changed in the upper right panel.

3 Obtaining and running the [GEANT4](#) applications

There are only a few steps/commands necessary to get the [GEANT4](#) application running.

First, open a terminal via `Activities->Terminal`.

⚠️ The default shell is `tcsh`.

The repository containing the **GEANT4** applications can then be cloned using the command:

```
1 git clone https://github.com/spearhead-he/G4VM.git
```

Now change to the build directory of the desired **GEANT4** application, e.g.:

```
1 cd G4VM/G4VM_build/
```

⚠ ARM based host systems: On ARM systems, first compile the binaries by running:

```
1 make
```

Compilation has been completed successfully if the following feedback is given:

```
1 [100%] Built target basic-sensi-gdml
```

You can now proceed as on Intel-Based Host systems.

Intel based Host Systems: The **GEANT4** application can then be run in QT-UI mode via:

```
1 ./Spearhead_G4VM
```

Models can be changed in `/run/vis.mac`

A simulation can be run with macro (to be added with **D2.3**) via:

```
1 ./Spearhead_G4VM <path_to_macro>
```


Figure 8: **GEANT4** model of **EPHIN** with spacecraft model run in the **G4VM** in UI mode.

4 Materials and volume names for the ERNE model

The ERNE model is a CAD model of the instrument reconstructed from sheet drawings. The CAD data is converted into Standard for the Exchange of Product model data (STEP) format² by the CAD itself. The resulting STEP model does not contain the hierarchy of the original CAD data but still retains all volumes as separate entities. Thus, there are no nested child volumes in the STEP structure, but all volumes are equal children within the World volume defined as a confining box.

The STEP file is further converted by pyg4ometry (Boogert et al. 2019) into GDML. Volume names are retained from the original CAD version and used for automatic material assignment. The prefixes used for automatic assignment and the corresponding materials are listed below. Materials with a prefix ending in "10" are artificially diluted to 10% density of the regular material.

```

1
2  material_mappings = {
3      "Al"      : "ALUMINUM",
4      "Al10"   : "ALUMINUM10",
5      "Component" : "PTFE",
6      "Detektori" : "SILICON",
7      "Cu"     : "COPPER",
8      "Epoxy"  : "Resin4PCB",
9      "Mylar"  : "G4_MYLAR",
10     "Kapton"  : "G4_KAPTON",
11     "ERTALON" : "G4_NYLON-6-6",
12     "Bronze"  : "G4_BRONZE",
13     "VITON"   : "G4_VITON",
14     "PCB"     : "FR-4",
15     "PEEK"    : "PEEK",
16     "PLA"     : "PLA",
17     "PTFE"    : "PTFE",
18     "Plastic" : "POLYPROPYLENE",
19     "Pt"      : "PLATINUM",
20     "Rh"      : "RHODIUM",
21     "SS"      : "STAINLESSSTEEL",
22     "Si"      : "SILICON",
23     "Si10"    : "SILICON10",
24     "SiO2"    : "SiO2",
25     "Silicone" : "SILICONE",
26     "Steel"   : "STEEL",
27     "Ta"      : "TANTALUM",
28     "GAGG"    : "GAGG",
29     "Al2SiO3" : "ALC",
30     "Al2O3"   : "G4_ALUMINUM_OXIDE",
31     "AL2O3"   : "G4_ALUMINUM_OXIDE",
32     "CsI"     : "CsI",
33     "BGO"     : "G4_BGO",
34     "Ag"      : "AG",
35     "W"       : "TUNGSTEN",
36     "BC_430"  : "G4_PLASTIC_SC_VINYLTOLUENE",
37     "BC_620"  : "G4_TITANIUM_DIOXIDE",
38     "Rubber"  : "G4_RUBBER_NATURAL",
39     "Tetrtec" : "G4_CELLULOSE_CELLOPHANE"
40 }

```

²https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_10303